

Report on Additive Manufacturing Materials
for OPTICON Work Package 5.1.1

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Nomenclature

AM	Additive Manufacturing
SS316	Stainless Steel 316
Ti 64	Alloy of Ti-6Al-4V
TNO	The Netherlands Organisation for applied scientific research
UoS	University of Sheffield
WP	Work Package

Work Package details

Work Package	Theme
5.1.1	Materials Group
5.1.2	Active Control
5.1.3	Cooled Mirrors
5.1.4	Embedded Fibres
5.2	Prototyping (Jan 2019)
5.3	AM cookbook and toolkit

1 Introduction

This work package (WP) is focussed on investigating the feasibility and practicality of using additive manufacturing (AM) for astronomical components. The work within the WP focused on the material selection process, but also covered important details about AM method and AM machines.

The benefits of AM are well known and many of the primary advantages that come with designing parts within AM are applicable to astronomical components. For example, benefits such as complex designs and rapid prototyping are widely applicable and offer the opportunity to significantly improve on conventionally made components.

The main objective of this WP is to inform and assist the design of AM components by astronomical scientists and engineers. Dissemination of this information will be done via this AM report and the WP report on WP 5.1.1. This AM report goes into more depth about background topics connected to both AM and astronomical instruments. There is also more detail about the process and decision making on the properties and materials that were analysed. The WP report is shorter and focuses more tightly on the work that was actually carried out within the WP.

It is also worth noting that while this report is about AM in general it will have a bias towards the methods, machines and materials that are available through the OPTI-CON partners that carry out AM. These are the University of Sheffield (UoS) and The Netherlands Organisation for applied scientific research (TNO).

2 Background - Additive Manufacturing

2.1 Overview

AM covers a very large range of methods and materials. The ASTM (American Section of the International Association for Testing Materials) classifies AM into seven different method types [1].

	Name	Associated Acronyms
1	Binder jetting	BJ
2	Direct energy deposition	DED
3	Material extrusion	FDM, FFF
4	Material jetting	MJ
5	Powder Bed Fusion	SLS, SLM
6	Sheet lamination	SL
7	Vat photopolymerisation	SLA, DLP

Within these seven methods there are then many more different energy sources, material delivery methods and materials. Many of these methods are unavailable to this WP or use materials unsuitable for the properties required in astronomical components.

This WP focuses primarily on metals and ceramics as these are the materials that are commonly used in many astronomical components. Polymers are less frequently used but are viable for some niche applications. This report will not investigate polymers experimentally, as there are some unfavourable materials properties such as high thermal expansion and poor strength. The report will cover some of the background information though.

An important part of AM production is the control of the building parameters. Compared to conventional production methods there are many more variables that can be

changed and many more options within each variable. However, refining and optimising these methods is largely avoided in this WP (and follow-on WPs) by using machines and materials that are already optimised.

2.2 Ceramic Production

Ceramic production within this WP is led by TNO. There are four main ceramic materials that are investigated: Al_2O_3 , SiC, SiSiC and ZrO_2 . These four materials are all potentially useful, with reasonable cost and properties that can be matched to the requirements of astronomical components. These components include optical mirrors [2], structural components [3] and X-ray mirrors [4] that have all been produced in ceramics for telescopes previously.

If there was a specific need and reason for pursuing a different ceramic this could be incorporated into future WPs. However, ceramic materials that are less commonly used in AM do have limited material property data and therefore come with an additional overhead in time and cost.

The ceramic materials can be produced in a number of different ways, each with different strengths and weaknesses and not all methods suitable for all materials. These methods include Selective Laser Sintering (SLS), Fused Deposition Modelling (FDM), Digital Light Projector (DLP) and Binder Jetting. Fig. 1 shows a binder jetting system. Exactly which method will be suitable is an issue that is more relevant to future WPs during the component design stage.

Figure 1: A binder jetting system. Controlling the two pistons allows the levelling roller to replenish the powder on top of the build. The inkjet printer will bind the powder together with the liquid adhesive in the appropriate place for the design. This process of adding a powder layer and selectively binding it is repeated until the build is complete. A sintering, and possibly a chemical treatment, will be necessary after the build has finished. Image from TNO internal presentation, image credit from Loughborough University [5].

These AM methods have different ways of delivering the powder and heat necessary to melt, fuse or sinter the materials. One common aspect for ceramic AM is the mechanism of delivering the powder. The ceramic powder is often suspended in a resin or some other type of solvent. The ceramic structure is then chemically treated and sintered to remove

the resin and form the solid structure. More detail on the methods can be found in AM guides [6–8].

2.3 Metal Production

Metal production is coordinated by UoS. The main metals that UoS work with are Ti64, stainless steel and inconel alloys. Other metals used less frequently used are aluminium, titanium aluminide and copper. Beyond these alloys there are several alloys that have been used for individual projects. As with the ceramics, the unusual alloys can be made available to this WP if required.

The most common AM method used by UoS is powder bed. A powder bed system uses a three step system. Powder is raked across the build stage, the laser melts a pattern according to the design and finally the stage is dropped to allow a new layer of powder to be raked across. The process then repeats until the build is complete. A diagram of this type of system can be found in Fig. 2.

The most common heat source used in these type of machine is a laser beam (or several laser beams). UoS has Renishaw and Aconity systems that use laser power and are accessible to this WP. These laser beams can be pulse or continuous and can have fully customisable parameters. For the Aconity systems there is also the option to have specific lasers for specific materials. This can be useful for certain materials, for example copper that is highly reflective to most lasers.

Figure 2: A simplified diagram of a powder bed system. The processing table lowers by a small increment (typically between 50 and 100 microns) as each layer is melted. Fresh powder can be fetched from hoppers, a rising platform or some other delivery system. Image from internal University of Sheffield presentation.

UoS also has Arcam systems that use an electron beam as the heat source. Electron beam systems have a slightly different process, with a brief sinter stage before the material is melted. The full details of the equipment can be found in the appendix in Section 13.

2.4 Polymers Production

Polymer AM is the most accessible and lowest cost material of all the AM technologies. This is due to low operating temperatures of the machines that require much less specialised equipment. Polymer AM is well known as an education tool and as part of rapid prototyping, but polymer AM technology is also used for many industrial applications.

The technology for polymer AM has less demanding requirements than metal and ceramic AM machines. There are polymer AM machines that operate in a similar way to the metal and ceramics machines discussed earlier, but there are also machines that operate with features and technology only possible with polymers. These include open air production, multiple feed stocks and simplistic heating elements [9, 10].

The materials selection for polymers is large. Many of the most commonly used polymers are suitable for AM, with each AM system tailored to control the temperatures and pressures accordingly. Materials like Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene (ABS), Polylactic Acid (PLA) and Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA) are all frequently used, as are many more polymers [11]. The range of polymers include thermoplastics, thermosets, blends and many other types. As with conventional manufacturing of polymers there can be customisation of colour and composition for functional or aesthetic reasons.

The flexibility of polymer AM has led to innovation that is not possible with the other materials. Polymer AM machines have the capacity to print in multiple materials. This can be used to design novel devices, for example metamaterials with tunable negative thermal expansion [12]. Polymer AM machines have also been adapted to allow electronics and circuitry to be integrated within structures.

2.5 Design Considerations

Overview

There are several perceived drawbacks of AM, these include: material properties, surface quality, and structural properties [13,14]. Surface finish is rougher than conventionally produced surfaces and structural properties can be reduced if there are voids or an undesirable microstructure.

These drawbacks can be improved upon with methodology and technique [15], adjusting and improving the parameters that are used for building. Alternatively, these detrimental properties can be improve with careful use of post processing [16]

One of the main attractions of AM is the amount of freedom that is offered when designing components. However there are limits and guidelines on what AM parts can be constructed. Some of these considerations are hard limits based on the machine in use (e.g. maximum size). Other considerations are not hard limits and are concerned with making builds more efficient, cost effective and reliable (e.g. avoiding overhangs).

Post processing of AM parts is a common practise and is used for a number of different reasons. Often this is a corrective process where the material properties achieved do not reach the standard required. However, there is a growing thought process that AM is best utilised in cooperation with conventional material processing rather than replacing it. This approach has been called ‘Hybrid Engineering’ [17] and has been investigated by academia and industry [18–20]. These post processes include, but are not limited to machining, heat treatments and surface coatings.

2.5.1 Materials Properties - Surface Quality

Often the drawbacks with AM can also be mitigated by using intelligent design and combining AM production with post processing methods. Surface quality for example can be

improved with machining or polishing. If significant machining is required then excess material can be factored into the build. Alternatively a better surface finish can be achieved by using surface coatings.

2.5.2 Materials Properties - Structural Properties

The structural properties of AM are difficult to control given how they depend on many factors. The bed temperatures, cooling rates and heating patterns all influence the structural properties of an AM build [21, 22]. The thermal conditions during the build, as they do with conventional metal forging, have an enormous impact on the structural properties of any piece. In addition the orientation of the build [23], the powder type [24] and powder quality [24] can all affect the properties. Due to this uncertainty the properties, specifically the stiffness, will be investigated as part of this work package.

2.5.3 Materials Properties - Metal Solidification

When producing conventional (non-AM) metal parts the solidification process has the primary impact upon the material properties and is something that needs to be controlled carefully to ensure material behaves as expected. The same is true for AM metals. Generally there is a rapid cooling rate, but it can vary significantly between machine and method.

The cooling rate also depends on the material, geometry and the size of the component that is being built. Problems within the cooling rate can lead to such defects as residual stresses or component cracking. If applications are particularly sensitive to these problems or other metal solidification effects then this should be during the development and prototyping processes.

2.5.4 Design Limitations - Component Size

For any AM machine there is a build envelope that defines the maximum dimensions of a part that can be built. There is also a maximum height. This height is usually limited by the range of z-axis motion on the AM machine but can also be limited by other factors such as limited powder or residual stresses. The difference in stresses between the top and bottom of a component is a frequent problem with laser based powder bed melting. It can be mitigated with heated beds and other mechanisms but it will likely still be a problem for especially tall parts.

2.5.5 Design Limitations - Build Accuracy

The build accuracy and minimum feature size of AM for many applications is not a significant factor. However, there are some applications where a very high degree of accuracy is required. In these examples it is standard practise to allow extra room in the build and then have the part machined down to the highly accurate size needed. Extra material is needed depends on the material, the design and the machining method.

2.5.6 Design Limitations - Overhangs

Overhangs, or negative space, is when material needs to be build without any solid material beneath it. Examples of this include arches, sandwich pieces and heavily angled structures. The problems with negative space relate to the different conditions that overhang material experiences. For example, in powder bed melting a negative space is surrounded by powder rather than bulk, so it experiences a much lower thermal conductivity [25]. The problems related to negative space vary significantly with machine type, material and general method [26]. Some examples of overhangs, and the negative effect they can have are shown in Fig. 3.

(a) A design for a test piece with several overhangs.

(b) Overhangs of 0.5mm thickness.

(c) Overhangs of 1mm thickness.

(d) Overhangs of 2mm thickness.

Figure 3: Example builds showing the detrimental effects that can occur with large overhangs. Significant warping can be seen on the thicker overhangs. These builds are made from Ti64 using an Arcam. Images from internal UoS presentation.

Overhangs can be most easily dealt with by orientating a build, for example, an arch printed upside down will be much easier to build than the right way up. If orientating the part is not feasible, then a redesign of the part maybe required. Often relatively subtle changes to the design can offer significant improvements to how well a component will form.

Another commonly used solution is to add support struts. These are thin pieces of material that are printed with the build in order to support the negative space. An example of this is shown in Fig. 4. The use of supports does mean that some material will be wasted and that some post processing will be necessary to remove the support struts.

(a) A part design with many overhangs and no support structure . (b) A part design with a support structure (shown in red) for the overhangs.

Figure 4: An example of a component that has many overhangs with and without the support structures. Support structures are produced using Magics and are tailored for building on an Arcam machine. Images from internal UoS presentation.

2.5.7 Post Processing - Machining

Machining, the removal of material to reach a specific shape, is a common form of post processing for AM components. The amount of material that may be removed can vary from fractions of a millimetre to significant parts of the components. Removing a thin layer from the surface will improve the surface finish of a product and will remove the pores that may have formed near the material surface. Machining of the material can also allow for highly precise configurations to be built.

2.5.8 Post Processing - Heat Treatment

Many AM processes, for example those that use resins or require a sinter stage, have a heat treatment as part of a standard production procedure. However, it is also fairly common for heat treatments to be carried out after production in order to change the material properties. Often this is to reduce the stresses that may have build up during a build. Residual stresses can be especially prevalent in builds that have large heat differences during the build process (for example SLM of a tall part will be prone to a large temperature gradient) [27]. Heat treatments can also be used to achieve microstructure changes like in conventional materials, for example annealing [28] or ageing [28].

Hot Isostatic Pressing (HIP) is another common heat treatment. This process, applying an elevated temperature under high pressure conditions, is used to improve the porosity of AM parts.

2.5.9 Post Processing - Surface Coatings

Surface coating processes work in much the same way as they do for conventional materials. The use in AM components may be particularly useful where the produced surface properties are vastly different than the desired surface properties.

There are many examples where surface coatings may be critical for astronomical components. A lightweight mirror printed in a low density material may need a surface coating (e.g. nickel-phosphorus) to achieve the surface properties required. Alternatively light may need to be absorbed rather than reflected and a black coating may be required.

3 Background - Astronomical Components

3.1 Applications

One of the principal goals of this WP is to evaluate selected AM materials for astronomical components. However, there are no materials requirements that are universal across astronomical instruments. In fact the range of possible instruments is extremely wide and the properties required for each component can vary significantly.

Investigating every possible relevant material property is not practical, so it is necessary to find a manageable number of key properties that are common and are the most likely to be useful in the future design processes. To aid this process a few key components were selected and their properties were investigated further. The components selected for analysis were mirrors, structural parts and embedded fibre parts.

evaluate selected AM materials for astronomical components.

3.1.1 Mirrors

There are multiple reasons why using AM for mirrors can offer improved performance. The most obvious and prominent of these potential improvements is the reduction in weight. Weight reduction is necessary as often mirrors need to be moved around as well as overall instrument weight constraints. Current light-weighting methods include removing material from the back of mirrors (see Fig. 5) and using low density materials like aluminium [29] or ceramics like Si/SiC [2].

Figure 5: Images of existing mirrors that were designed without using AM. The left image shows the CAD file for a honeycomb design. The right image shows a mirror with triangle supports. The honeycomb and triangle designs are lighter than a solid mirror but could be made significantly lighter using AM design methods. Image from Carolyn Atkins and Glyndwr Innovations.

The main function of any mirror is the capture and accurate reflection of light. Any distortions or defects upon the optical surface reduces the efficiency of the mirror to reflect light and in turn the science that can be investigated.. Materials for mirrors must therefore not sag (high stiffness), not change shape significantly with temperature (low and predictable coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE)), not have defects on the surface (no porosity) and be polishable (high hardness and resistant to delamination).

Mirrors are used for capturing all types of light from infrared [30] to X-ray [31]. Detection of some of these wavelengths of light require cold temperature and vacuum conditions. Any component, including the mirror, may need to function in high or even ultra-high vac-

uum conditions. This means the outgassing needs to be low and the structure be fully dense with minimal voids or pores. Outgassing is not important for all mirrors though, there are many mirrors that operate at room temperature and in normal atmospheric conditions.

There are AM technologies that have been refined for a smooth and accurate surface finish [32,33]. It is unlikely though that even these refined methods could reach the level of accuracy necessary for astronomical mirrors. The AM technology available to this WP is certainly not able to achieve the polished finish that is required, meaning that post-process polishing is a necessary step. Given that polishing will always be needed the surface finish and surface accuracy for mirrors are of relatively low importance.

Low thermal conductivity can result in mirrors cooling unevenly which could lead to problems with distortion or even the complete failure of the part. A high thermal conductivity will mean the mirror cools more uniformly across the volume of the mirror and will be easier to cool down and heat up during the operation of the telescope.

3.1.2 Structural

Structural parts of astronomical instruments may appear to have a simpler brief than many of the highly specialised components. However, structural parts can make up a large fraction of the weight of an instrument and a defective structure can cause catastrophic and extremely costly problems for instruments. An example of structural part is shown in Fig. 6.

Figure 6: A CCD mount from the HiPERCAM setup that has been attached to multiple telescopes. There are multiple solid parts in this mount. All of these could be redesigned using AM to save weight. Image from Vik Dhillon [34].

For most astronomical instruments it is imperative for the function of the components that they are located correctly with a high degree of accuracy. It is therefore important that the structural part holding the components in place are similarly accurate and do not change with conditions. Similar to the mirrors, parts must be lightweight, stiff and have a predictable response to temperature changes.

Structural parts are used in the full range of astronomical components. It is likely that some parts will need to have suitable vacuum properties while other parts will operate under normal temperature and pressure conditions. Decisions about what level of outgassing is suitable will be made in other work packages by the engineers responsible for instrument design.

The accuracy limits of AM production may have an influence on material selection.

The ability of materials to be made to the dimensions required is an important property. However, for some structural parts there are cases where an ultra-high degree of precision is required (e.g. screw thread, hole alignment). In these high-precision examples, where post-processing will be needed regardless of how accurate the AM production was, the accuracy is not too significant.

3.1.3 Embedded Fibre Parts

WP 5.1.4 within the OPTICON project is dedicated to investigating embedded fibres. This WP is attempting to design parts that have fibre optic cables running throughout. This may be used as part a multi-signal switch or a relay.

The material properties required for the operation are likely to be similar to the other parts analysed. CTE, outgassing and surface accuracy will all be important in order to not break the extremely thin and fragile fibre optics.

WP 5.1.4 will also have to devise a suitable method for inserting the cables into any part. The cables may be inserted to the AM part after it has been produced, but it may turn out that the cables are introduced beforehand. It is therefore necessary to detail the melting temperature of the materials and the methods that can be used for each material. Due to the temperature limitations this is an application where polymer printing may offer the best solution.

3.2 Material Properties

Analysis of the astronomical components showed a few key properties that are likely to important across most if not all parts. These properties will be listed with highest priority when collecting data in Table 1. Not mentioned so far but still of high importance is the cost. The cost can be split into the powder cost, AM production cost and post processing costs. It is difficult to quantify these costs as they will depend on details that are currently

unknown (e.g. machine availability) and will also depend heavily on the specific designs of the parts that are being built.

There are some further material properties that have not been listed so far but will be included, albeit with a lower priority. These properties have a lower priority as they are only important for a few specific parts or do not require optimisation. Examples of this are electrical resistivity which is only important for electrically operated parts, or ductility where as long as the material is not brittle it does not need to be considered further.

4 Method - Experiment Selection

The main assignment that needed to be completed for this WP is the collection of all the necessary data for all the relevant AM materials. The first task was to decide which values could be found from literature and which values needed to be measured. The factors influencing this decision were based on cost and time as well as which experiments were likely to be most useful.

The vast majority of the properties, both of high and low priority, were able to be found from literature. Remeasuring fundamental values of materials (e.g. density and thermal conductivity) were not deemed optimum use of resource. The majority of these properties for AM materials can be assumed to be the same as the conventionally produced equivalent. It was decided for strategic benefit to the programme to measure the stiffness, to analyse the porosity and to produce a sample lattice.

The assumption that AM produced materials behave similarly, in terms of mechanical properties, to conventionally produced materials is more suitable for ceramics than metals. The processing routes of ceramics (conventional and AM) are quite similar and so the resultant properties are also similar. This is also supported by a number of reports that confirm the similar mechanical properties [35, 36].

The properties of AM produced metal parts do not always match the conventionally produced equivalent. Similar, or even enhanced, mechanical properties using AM can be achieved in metals; however, conversely, there are many examples of AM metal parts having worse mechanical properties [37]. Due to this potential property difference the experimental measurements in this work will focus on the metals.

The stiffness was selected for measurement as it is one the highest priority properties with almost all astronomical components requiring a high stiffness value. There is also the possibility that AM-produced materials may have different stiffness values than equivalent conventionally produced material.

The porosity was analysed as it serves two functions. First porosity has a detrimental effect on the quality of mirrors. Significant porosity can not be polished out and will limit the quality of the mirror; the second function is that porosity can be used as an approximation of outgassing performance. The theory that if a material is fully dense and without pores then the material should outgas according to the literature value. If there are pores then that the outgassing performance will be poor. Formal outgassing measurements may be taken as part of the prototyping process in subsequent WPs.

The sample lattice was selected as a quick test of build quality. The lattice showcases the ability of a material to be made into a lattice as well as the quality of the surface. The results from this experiment are important for concepts for future designs. It shows that bold and radical weight saving designs can and should be attempted.

The list of properties that were collected are included in Table 1. The properties are ranked by priority and whether they were used for selecting the preliminary test materials.

Table 1: The list of properties that were used for selecting preliminary materials and will be used for selecting materials in future WPs.

Property	Importance	Used for selection
Specific stiffness	Highest	Yes
Coefficient Thermal Expansion (CTE)	Highest	Yes
Outgassing	Highest	Yes
Modulus of elasticity	High	Yes
Density	High	Yes
Thermal Conductivity	High	Yes
Hardness	High	Yes
Porosity	High	Yes
Electrical Resistivity	Medium	No
Specific heat capacity	Medium	No
Strength	Medium	No
Ductility	Medium	No
Shear modulus	Low	No
Poisson Ratio	Low	No

5 Method - Material Selection

This section relates to which materials should be detailed using literature values and which materials should have the experimental measurements (stiffness, porosity, etc.). The full list of materials that have been used in AM is incredibly large; when this list is down-selected to those materials that are available to UoS and TNO and those materials that are not

patented or prohibitively expensive, the list decreases to approximately ten materials to investigate.

The UoS-TNO materials list was further down-selected for experimental study based on materials deemed to have strategic importance - i.e. those materials currently used in astronomical components, or materials with high beneficial properties. This down-selection was important to ensure that resources were appropriately focussed to minimise repetition of experiments on materials that would not be used. For the materials where experimentation has not been undertaken, property values have been referenced to literature.

This WP will compile literature values and experimentally measured values for a number of metals and ceramics. For the most part the composition of the materials is identical for the literature values and the samples that were produced for experimental measurements. However, for the aluminium alloy of interest it was necessary to use slightly different grades. The aluminium alloy from the literature was Al10SiMg and the alloy used experimentally was Al339. These are both high silicon aluminium alloys with only marginally different silicon content (12% compared to 10%) and similar other elements.

6 Method - Practical Measurements

6.1 Stiffness Measurements

Stiffness measurements were made using a 3-point bend test. A universal testing machine Zwick/Roell ProLine Z050 machine was used for all measurements. The size gap for the measurements was 56 mm with a 5 kN load cell applying the load in the middle of this span. The test samples were cylinders with a length of 80 mm and a diameter of 2mm. This arrangement is shown in Fig. 7.

(a) Bend testing at first contact.

(b) Significant bending in the sample.

Figure 7: The bend testing of a SS316 rod.

6.2 Sample Lattice

The sample lattice was used to demonstrate the accuracy and quality of AM lattice builds. As there are no formal measurements to carry out on the lattice the design can vary. For the metal samples the lattice was a 0.25mm thickness diamond lattice forming a 25mm cube.

Figure 8: Two sample metal lattices. The Ti64 lattice is on the left and the SS316 lattice is on the right.

There are many previous examples of ceramic lattices that have been produced by TNO. These have been produced in both Al_2O_3 and SiSiC using a variety of different methods. An example Al_2O_3 lattice is shown in Fig. 9. The example lattice is a cuboid of $(50 \times 25 \times 10)$ mm with a diamond structure of 0.5 mm.

Figure 9: An Al_2O_3 lattice.

6.3 Porosity Measurements

Porosity investigations could not be carried out on the stiffness and lattice samples. Many AM processes can result in extra porosity close to the a build surface [38]. Measuring the porosity in samples where most or all of the volume is close to a surface (i.e. made of thin parts) would produce unfair results. An additional cube of 10mm was therefore produced so that porosity could be measured in the bulk of a sample as well as near the surface.

Porosity measurements were carried out using an Olympus BX51 Clemex microscope using the INCA software. This software allows for automated measurements and analysis to be carried out, vastly increasing the volume and detail of porosity data that can be collected. This may be of use for components where even a small amount of porosity would be problematic (e.g. mirror surfaces).

The SS316 porosity sample was produced using the Aconity Mini at UoS. This combi-

nation of material and machined have been used previously and so there were parameters (controlling the laser beam) available to use for building. Three SS316 micrographs, two from the centre and one from the corner, are shown in Fig. 10.

The micrographs in Fig. 10 show that SS316 is largely pore free Fig. 10a shows almost no porosity. Fig. 10b does show some pores in the bulk of the material. Fig. 10c shows that there is more porosity in the corner of the sample but that it is still relatively pore free.

The Ti64 porosity sample was produced using the Arcam Q20+ at UoS. This machine is used exclusively for Ti64 and so has parameters that have been optimised for this material. However, the coarser powder and more violent nature of the machine (using electron beam rather than laser beam) can lead to more porosity in AM parts. The micrographs from the Ti64 sample is shown in Fig. 11.

The micrographs in Fig. 11 show more porosity is present in the Ti64 sample than the SS316 sample. There is also more porosity around the edge of the part compared to the centre. This was expected as previous results and papers have detailed this effect in electron beam produced parts [38].

The Al339 sample was produced using the Aconity Mini at UoS. The department has limited experience building with aluminium and no experience working with this particular grade of aluminium. The Aconity Mini has saved build parameters for materials, including aluminium. However, these parameters are not optimised and are not tailored for particular grades of aluminium. The micrographs from the Al339 sample is shown in Fig. 12. There is a significant amount of porosity throughout the sample.

(a) SS316 centre micrograph showing minimal porosity. (b) SS316 centre micrograph showing the presence of some pores.

(c) SS316 corner micrograph.

Figure 10: SS316 micrographs, taken using the Clemex as previously described.

(a) Ti64 centre micrograph.

(b) Ti64 corner micrograph.

Figure 11: Ti64 micrographs, taken using the Clemex as previously described.

(a) Al339 centre micrograph.

(b) Al339 corner micrograph.

Figure 12: Al339 micrographs, taken using the Clemex as previously described.

7 Stiffness Results

Stiffness samples were produced for Ti64, SS316 and Al339. The Ti64 and SS316 samples were tested but the samples produced for Al339 were unsuitable for testing. Due to insufficient heating on the support struts the samples had bent slightly during the manufacturing process. Also, given the significant porosity of the Al339 parts the bend results would not be a fair representation. The Al339 measurements will have to be revisited once the porosity has been improved.

The samples were tested using the method described in Section 6.1. Results from a Ti64 sample and SS316 sample are shown in Fig. 13.

Figure 13: Two example force-extension graphs for the metal bend testing.

The results of the testing were that Ti64 and SS316 had elastic moduli of 77 ± 5 GPa and 97 ± 6 GPa respectively. This is lower than the literature values of 113.8 GPa for Ti64 and 193 GPa for SS316. The exact reason why the values are lower is unclear. It is likely connected to some combination of the microstructure, grain shape or porosity. This is discussed further in Section 10.1.

8 Alumina Investigation

Prior to this WP TNO, with Delft University, had carried out a comprehensive study on the difference between conventionally manufactured alumina and AM alumina [39]. This study was primarily to investigate body armour but the physical and mechanical results are useful for all ceramic applications.

The main tests were done were done by analysing the ballistic properties of the two different alumina sources. Alumina discs (see Fig. 14) were mounted into a specially designed rig and tested using the energy method [39]. The results showed that AM alumina behaved similarly to the conventional alumina.

Figure 14: AM alumina discs in the ballistic study. Image from Carton and Weerheijm [39].

The physical properties of the alumina were also broadly similar. The AM alumina had a slightly lower density (3.76 g/cm³) compared to the conventional alumina (3.93 g/cm³).

However, this slight difference in density has little effect on the mechanical properties (see Table 2).

Table 2: A summary of the alumina data from Carton and Weerheijm [39] .

Type:	Density (g/cm ³)	Shear Modulus (GPa)	Youngs Modulus (GPa)	Bulk Modulus (GPa)	Poisson Ratio (-)	Hardness Hv (GPa)	Toughness K1C (MPa.m ^{0.5})
AM Produced	3.76	227	358	227	0.24	18.4	2.9
Conventional	3.93	221	363	220	0.225	14.9	2.8

9 Literature values

The literature values for the AM materials are shown in Table 3 and Table 4. Outgassing measurements are difficult to compare fairly due to the significant effects that the sample preparation has on the results. The samples may have different cleanliness, surface finish, baking conditions and test parameters.

The baking of the samples refers to the heat treatments that are often used for vacuum suitable materials. The difference in these conditions can mean that there are orders of magnitude difference in measured value. The baking of samples makes a particular difference with water vapour. Unbaked samples can contain small amounts of water vapour which drastically impact the outgassing performance. Baked samples, especially ones that have had a high temperature for a long duration, should have no water vapour present. The outgassing of these samples will be gas atoms, most likely nitrogen or dissolved hydrogen depending on the material [40]. The results, with all of the qualifying information about the measurement, can be found in Table 5.

Table 3: The literature values for the AM metal materials. A refers to ASM [41] and B refers to Amesweb [42]

Material	Ti ^A	Ti64 ^A	SS316 ^B	Al 4032 ^B	In 718 ^{A,B}	Cu ^B
Specific stiffness (GPa*cc/g)	23.3	25.7	24.1	29.3	25.4	14.2
Lin CTE (x10e-6 /K)	8.6	8.6	16	18	13	16.4
Outgassing	This row shows the relative priority. See Table 5 for details.					
Mod Elasticity (Gpa)	105	113.8	193	78.6	208	110
Density (g/cc)	4.51	4.43	8	2.68	8.19	7.764
Therm Cond (W/m-K)	16.4	6.7	16.3	138	11.4	385
Hardness	145	349	482	137	364	50
Elec resist (ohm-cm)	5.2e-5	17.8e-5	7.4e-5	0.5e-5	12.5e-5	0.17e-5
Spec Heat Cap (J/gK)	0.523	0.5263	0.5	0.85	0.435	0.385
Strength (Uts) (MPa)	344	950	580	379	1100	210
Ductility (Elong, %)	20	14	50	9	25	60
Shear Modulus (GPa)	45	44	77	26	80	46
Poisson Ratio	0.37	0.342	0.25	0.34	0.294	0.343

Table 4: The literature values for the AM ceramic materials. C refers to matweb [43] and D refers to AZOM [44]

Material	Al ₂ O ₃ ^{C,D}	Si SiC ^{C,D}	SiC ^{C,D}
Specific stiffness (GPa*cc/g)	83.1	122.1	135.6
Lin CTE (x10e-6 /K)	7.2	3.8	3.7
Outgassing	See Table 5 for details on outgassing.		
Mod Elasticity (Gpa)	300	350-400	434
Density	3.69	3.07	3.2
Therm Cond (W/m-K)	18	40	120
Hardness	2660	1200 (Si), 2700 (SiC)	2800
Elec resist (ohm-cm)	>10e14	1.0	10e2 - 10e6
Spec Heat Cap (J/gK)	880	0.7	580
Strength (Uts) (MPa)	124	350	240-1625
Ductility (Elong)	0.018	0.01-0.4	0.01-0.4
Shear Modulus	124	169	179
Poisson Ratio	0.21	0.17	0.187

Table 5: Various outgassing results for the materials of interest in this WP.

Material	Conditions	Outgassing rate (torr-L/sec-cm ²)	Ref
Aluminium	None	1×10^{-6}	Fermi Lab [45]
Aluminium	Degassed 24hr., degreased and cleaned	4.14×10^{-9}	Fermi Lab [45]
Al ₂ O ₃	Clean, after a few hours of pumping	1×10^{-8} to 10^{-9}	Princeton [46]
Al ₂ O ₃	24 hr. bake at 400 °C	1×10^{-14} to $^{-15}$	Princeton [46]
Al 6061-T6	10 hrs baking	2.5×10^{-8}	Princeton [46]
Al 6061-T6	13.5 hrs baking at 300 °C	1.4×10^{-8}	Fermi Lab [45]
SiC	None	9×10^{-13}	INFN [47]
SS316	Unbaked	3.2×10^{-9}	KIT [48]
SS316	Various baking condition	1.7×10^{-9} to 3×10^{-12}	KIT [48]
Ti64	None stated	1.8×10^{-9}	Princeton [46]

10 Discussion

The literature values show that there are many suitable materials, both metal and ceramic, for use in astronomical components. Some of these materials are already used in astronomical parts but some, such as Ti64, are not. Assigning specific materials to specific components is not part of this WP will aid scientists and engineers in finding a suitable material for a given application.

10.1 Stiffness

The stiffness results showed a noticeable difference between the AM produced samples and the expected values found from literature. The source of the difference is unclear and will require further investigation. Heat treatments may improve the properties by changing the grain size (annealing or quenching) or by removing porosity (HIPing). This will be the subject of a further investigation.

Another potential reason for the lower stiffness values may be the build parameters. Building with different power settings and different build orientations will be the basis of another stiffness investigation. Related to the build parameters is the effect that the edge porosity has on the stiffness values. This can be investigated by varying the thickness of the test samples, and will form part of the stiffness investigation.

10.2 Porosity

Two of the metals, Ti64 and SS316, were relatively pore free. Whether the porosity levels are suitable for some of the specialised criteria of telescope components is not known though. This low level of porosity might have a significant impact on the outgassing performance of these materials. One way to improve the porosity is to HIP the parts. However, before deciding whether to HIP parts or not it will be worth investigating if the pores are making a difference to the outgassing and if the HIPing of parts makes a difference.

For mirrors, controlling the porosity in the vicinity of the optical surface is of high importance; even low porosity would increase the scatter from the mirror surface. There may be standard ways to improve the porosity of components (e.g. build parameters and HIPing) but there may be other approaches that could be useful for mirrors. Given that the mirror only has one polished surface any porosity on other surfaces or in the bulk is relatively unimportant. Therefore, it may be the case that a strategy that has more overall

porosity but with one surface that is pore-free, may be the best approach for mirrors. The challenges of minimising porosity and controlling where the pores form will be the subject of another investigation.

The Al339 sample exhibited a significant amount of porosity. It will therefore be necessary to optimise the melt strategy for this material. To date this has not been possible, but new build plates will be arriving and experiments will be carried out then.

10.3 Lattices

The sample lattice showed that some level of intricacy is possible with all of the featured materials. These samples lattices did not test the limits of intricacy though, and much finer features may be possible. This will depend on the material, AM technique and the orientation of the build.

11 Future Work

11.1 Further Investigations

The experiments carried out so far have been useful in investigating the intricacy, porosity and stiffness of the AM samples. However, the experiments have also identified a number of areas that will need to be investigated further. These investigations are:-

- The stiffness properties with respect to build parameters and orientations.
- The stiffness properties with respect to heat treatments.
- The outgassing properties.
- The porosity of samples and controlling the pore location.
- Optimising the aluminium build parameters.

It is anticipated that one or two builds and experimental measurements should suffice for each mini-project. The priority of these further investigations will depend on the decisions made as part of WP 5.2. Once the theme of the prototypes (e.g. mirrors, structural parts, etc.) has been decided this will inform which further investigations are the most useful.

11.2 Prototyping Options (WP 5.2)

Within this OPTICON programme there are 3 further sub-WPs investigating the suitability AM for different astronomical components - these WPs are detailed below.

- 5.1.2 - Active Control
- 5.1.3 - Cooled Mirrors
- 5.1.4 - Embedded Fibres

These work packages have worked in parallel to WP5.1.1 and have been investigating concepts for the future WP 5.2. There were over forty prototypes from these WPs with some combining facets of multiple WPs. To make future decisions about prototypes it was decided to group these prototypes into five themes, namely:-

- Embedded fibres.
- Heat transfers.
- Mirrors.
- Structural parts.
- Switches

Once the prototype themes have been established this will shape the direction for WP 5.2.

12 Conclusion

WP 5.1.1 investigated several AM materials to be implemented within ground-based optical and IR astronomical instrumentation. Many of the materials possess desirable properties that are widely applicable to astronomical components. These is also a reasonable choice of materials, with several metals and ceramics detailed in this report. There are also details and advice about design rules for AM.

This WP has collected and collated a lot of data for materials in AM. However, it has also revealed some areas where further research is required. Research areas such as outgassing and improving the stiffness properties are worthwhile studies that may be publishable in their own rights. These investigations will be carried out in the near future and will feed into the prototyping work.

There is the potential for innovative and bold designs, in both ceramics and metals, in the upcoming prototyping work (WP 5.2). This WP will serve as useful information during the decision process (about which prototypes to advance) as well as the longer development process of astronomical components.

References

- [1] Ian Gibson, David Rosen, and Brent Stucker. Development of additive manufacturing technology, 01 2015.
- [2] Yumin Zhang, Jianhan Zhang, Jiecai Han, Xiaodong He, and Wang Yao. Large-scale fabrication of lightweight si/sic ceramic composite optical mirror. *Materials Letters*, 58(7):1204 – 1208, 2004.
- [3] A. Arvind, Rakesh Kumar, M.N. Deo, V.K. Shrikhande, and G.P. Kothiyal. Preparation, structural and thermo-mechanical properties of lithium aluminum silicate glass–

- ceramics. *Ceramics International*, 35(4):1661 – 1666, 2009.
- [4] S. Tsuneta, L. Acton, M. Bruner, J. Lemen, W. Brown, R. Carvalho, R. Catura, S. Freeland, B. Jurcevich, M. Morrison, Y. Ogawara, T. Hirayama, and J. Owens. The soft x-ray telescope for the solar-a mission. *Solar Physics*, 136(1):37–67, Nov 1991.
- [5] Loughborough University. <http://www.lboro.ac.uk/research/amrg/about/the7categoriesofadditivemanufacturing/binderjetting/>, 2014.
- [6] Kaufui V Wong and Aldo Hernandez. A review of additive manufacturing. *ISRN Mechanical Engineering*, 2012, 2012.
- [7] Flaviana Calignano, Diego Manfredi, Elisa Paola Ambrosio, Sara Biamino, Mariangela Lombardi, Eleonora Atzeni, Alessandro Salmi, Paolo Minetola, Luca Iuliano, and Paolo Fino. Overview on additive manufacturing technologies. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 105(4):593–612, 2017.
- [8] Brett P. Conner, Guha P. Manogharan, Ashley N. Martof, Lauren M. Rodomsky, Caitlyn M. Rodomsky, Dakesha C. Jordan, and James W. Limperos. Making sense of 3-d printing: Creating a map of additive manufacturing products and services. *Additive Manufacturing*, 1-4:64 – 76, 2014. Inaugural Issue.
- [9] John Ryan C. Dizon, Alejandro H. Espera, Qiyi Chen, and Rigoberto C. Advincula. Mechanical characterization of 3d-printed polymers. *Additive Manufacturing*, 20:44 – 67, 2018.
- [10] Mohammad Vaezi, Srisit Chianrabutra, Brian Mellor, and Shoufeng Yang. Multiple material additive manufacturing – part 1: a review. *Virtual and Physical Prototyping*, 8(1):19–50, 2013.
- [11] All3DP. 2018 3d printer filament guide – all you need to know, 2018.

- [12] Qiming Wang, Julie A. Jackson, Qi Ge, Jonathan B. Hopkins, Christopher M. Spadacini, and Nicholas X. Fang. Lightweight mechanical metamaterials with tunable negative thermal expansion. *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 117:175901, Oct 2016.
- [13] A. Townsend, N. Senin, L. Blunt, R.K. Leach, and J.S. Taylor. Surface texture metrology for metal additive manufacturing: a review. *Precision Engineering*, 46:34 – 47, 2016.
- [14] T. DebRoy, H.L. Wei, J.S. Zuback, T. Mukherjee, J.W. Elmer, J.O. Milewski, A.M. Beese, A. Wilson-Heid, A. De, and W. Zhang. Additive manufacturing of metallic components – process, structure and properties. *Progress in Materials Science*, 92:112 – 224, 2018.
- [15] Qingbo Jia and Dongdong Gu. Selective laser melting additive manufacturing of inconel 718 superalloy parts: Densification, microstructure and properties. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, 585:713–721, 2014.
- [16] Bandar AlMangour and Jenn-Ming Yang. Improving the surface quality and mechanical properties by shot-peening of 17-4 stainless steel fabricated by additive manufacturing. *Materials and Design*, 110:914 – 924, 2016.
- [17] Danielle Strong, Michael Kay, Brett Conner, Thomas Wakefield, and Guha Manogharan. Hybrid manufacturing – integrating traditional manufacturers with additive manufacturing (am) supply chain. *Additive Manufacturing*, 21:159 – 173, 2018.
- [18] Olivier Kerbrat, Pascal Mognol, and Jean-Yves Hascoët. A new dfm approach to combine machining and additive manufacturing. *Computers in Industry*, 62(7):684–692, 2011.

- [19] Erin M Betts (NASA). Cutting more than metal: How new technology and flexible engineering can enable affordable space missions, 2014.
- [20] KP Karunakaran, S Suryakumar, Vishal Pushpa, and Sreenathbabu Akula. Low cost integration of additive and subtractive processes for hybrid layered manufacturing. *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing*, 26(5):490–499, 2010.
- [21] Haider Ali, Le Ma, Hassan Ghadbeigi, and Kamran Mumtaz. In-situ residual stress reduction, martensitic decomposition and mechanical properties enhancement through high temperature powder bed pre-heating of selective laser melted ti6al4v. *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, 695:211–220, 2017.
- [22] William J Sames, Kinga A Unocic, Ryan R Dehoff, Tapasvi Lolla, and Sudarsanam S Babu. Thermal effects on microstructural heterogeneity of inconel 718 materials fabricated by electron beam melting. *Journal of Materials Research*, 29(17):1920–1930, 2014.
- [23] Ruben Wauthle, Bey Vrancken, Britt Beynaerts, Karl Jorissen, Jan Schrooten, Jean-Pierre Kruth, and Jan Van Humbeeck. Effects of build orientation and heat treatment on the microstructure and mechanical properties of selective laser melted ti6al4v lattice structures. *Additive Manufacturing*, 5:77–84, 2015.
- [24] Adriaan B Spierings and G Levy. Comparison of density of stainless steel 316l parts produced with selective laser melting using different powder grades. In *Proceedings of the Annual International Solid Freeform Fabrication Symposium*, pages 342–353. Austin, TX, 2009.
- [25] C.J. Smith, F. Derguti, E. Hernandez Nava, M. Thomas, S. Tammam-Williams, S. Gulizia, D. Fraser, and I. Todd. Dimensional accuracy of electron beam melting

- (ebm) additive manufacture with regard to weight optimized truss structures. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, 229:128 – 138, 2016.
- [26] Ahmed Hussein, Liang Hao, Chunze Yan, Richard Everson, and Philippe Young. Advanced lattice support structures for metal additive manufacturing. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, 213(7):1019 – 1026, 2013.
- [27] Beth E. Carroll, Todd A. Palmer, and Allison M. Beese. Anisotropic tensile behavior of ti-6al-4v components fabricated with directed energy deposition additive manufacturing. *Acta Materialia*, 87:309 – 320, 2015.
- [28] A. Popovich, V. Sufiarov, I. Polozov, E. Borisov, D. Masaylo, and A. Orlov. Microstructure and mechanical properties of additive manufactured copper alloy. *Materials Letters*, 179:38 – 41, 2016.
- [29] Masao Tokunari, Takanori Saito, Shinji Miyoki, Masatake Ohashi, and Kazuaki Kuroda. Optical properties measurement of an al 2 o 3 mirror substrate for the large-scale cryogenic gravitational wave telescope (lrgt). *Classical and Quantum Gravity*, 27(18):185015, 2010.
- [30] Infrared astronomy. *New Scientist*, 207(2776):ii – iii, 2010.
- [31] David N. Burrows, J. E. Hill, J. A. Nousek, J. A. Kennea, A. Wells, J. P. Osborne, A. F. Abbey, A. Beardmore, K. Mukerjee, A. D. T. Short, G. Chincarini, S. Campana, O. Citterio, A. Moretti, C. Pagani, G. Tagliaferri, P. Giommi, M. Capalbi, F. Tamburelli, L. Angelini, G. Cusumano, H. W. Bräuninger, W. Burkert, and G. D. Hartner. The swift x-ray telescope. *Space Science Reviews*, 120(3):165–195, Oct 2005.
- [32] Narendran Raghavan, Srdjan Simunovic, Ryan Dehoff, Alex Plotkowski, John Turner, Michael Kirka, and Suresh Babu. Localized melt-scan strategy for site specific control of

- grain size and primary dendrite arm spacing in electron beam additive manufacturing. *Acta Materialia*, 140:375 – 387, 2017.
- [33] Dazhong Wu, Yupeng Wei, and Janis Terpenney. Predictive modelling of surface roughness in fused deposition modelling using data fusion. *International Journal of Production Research*, 0(0):1–15, 2018.
- [34] Vik Dhillon. Hipercam, 2017.
- [35] Jan Deckers, Jozef Vleugels, and J P. Kruthl. Additive manufacturing of ceramics: A review. *Journal of Ceramic Science and Technology*, 5:245–260, 12 2014.
- [36] Martin Schwentenwein and Johannes Homa. Additive manufacturing of dense alumina ceramics. *International Journal of Applied Ceramic Technology*, 12, 09 2014.
- [37] John J. Lewandowski and Mohsen Seifi. Metal additive manufacturing: A review of mechanical properties. *Annual Review of Materials Research*, 46(1):151–186, 2016.
- [38] S. Tammam-Williams, H. Zhao, F. Léonard, F. Derguti, I. Todd, and P.B. Prangnell. Xct analysis of the influence of melt strategies on defect population in ti-6al-4v components manufactured by selective electron beam melting. *Materials Characterization*, 102:47 – 61, 2015.
- [39] Erik Carton and Jaap Weerheijm. Ballistic testing of small 3d-printed alumina disks with the energy method. 01 2016.
- [40] Rebecca Grinham and Dr Andrew Chew. A review of outgassing and methods for its reduction. *Applied Science and Convergence Technology*, 26:95–109, 09 2017.
- [41] Asm matweb database, 2018.
- [42] Amesweb database, 2018.

- [43] Matweb database, 2018.
- [44] Azo materials database, 2018.
- [45] M. Wong (Fermi Lab). Review of papers regarding vacuum system and materials, 2018.
- [46] J. L. Cecchi (Princeton). Review of papers regarding vacuum system and materials, 2018.
- [47] P. Chimenti R. Di Raddo V. Lollo S. Bini, V. Chimenti. Outgassing rate measurements of silicon carbide, 2018.
- [48] Katharina Battes, Christian Day, and V Hauer. Outgassing rate measurements of stainless steel and polymers using the difference method. *Journal of Vacuum Science and Technology A Vacuum, Surfaces, and Films*, 33:021603, 03 2015.

13 Appendix - Metal AM Details

Table 6 shows the details of the AM machines available at UoS. However, much of the information in the chart has caveats and requires further explanation. This section explains some of these extra details.

The minimum feature size listed is only a guideline with the size listed is not a guarantee that size can be reached, but it equally might prove to be a pessimistic value. The smallest feature size for each machine and material are found by optimising the build parameters. This process may have already been carried out or it might be a necessary part of the prototyping stage.

The dimensions that are listed for each machine are the true maximum dimensions. However, stress cracking and having to fill the build volume with expensive powder may limit the actual maximum dimensions of any component. The amount the maximum dimension is reduced depends entirely on the machine and the material that is in use.

The BeAM has an additional size constraint. The chamber is extremely large, and can accommodate the large sizes listed, but there is a weight limit of 15kg on the build plate.

The details listed for the Aconity machines are changeable. The concept and design of the Aconity machines is that they are open source and can be adapted to suit specific materials or designs. If none of the machines appear suitable for a specific material then adapting one of the Aconity machines could be potentially useful.

The Renishaw 250 and Arcam Q10 are not located in the materials department of UoS. They are located at the Royce Discovery Centre located just outside of Sheffield. This means that access is possible to these machines but might incur longer delays than the other machines.

Table 6: The details of metal AM machines available.

Machine Name	Delivery of material	Heat System	Power Input (W)	Build volume (mm)	Common materials	Other materials
Renishaw 125	Powder bed	Laser	150	125×125×100	Steel, SS, Ti64	Al
Arcam S12	Powder bed	E Beam	3000	210×210×250	Ti, Ti64, Inc, CoCr	HEAs, BMG, TiAl
Arcam S12	Powder bed	E Beam	3000	210×210×250	Ti, Ti64, Inc, CoCr	HEAs, BMG, TiAl
Arcam Q20+	Powder bed	E Beam	3000	350 (diam)×380	Ti64	None
BeAM 2.0	Material jetting	Laser	2000	1200×800×800	Ti64	Inconel
Aconity Mini	Powder bed	Laser	200	140 (diam)×85	Ti64, Inc, SS	Al
Aconity Lab	Powder bed	Laser	400	170 (diam)×170	Ti64, Inc, SS	Al
Renishaw 250	Powder bed	Laser	400	250×250×300	Steel, SS, Ti64	None
Arcam Q10	Powder bed	E Beam	3000	210×210×250	Ti64, TiAl	None

14 Appendix - Ceramic AM Details

There are many different machines and technologies available for ceramic production. Listing all of the available machines would be difficult, especially as the machines are spread out across multiple companies and divisions. Instead, a summary of the details by each method is more useful. The available technologies are

1. SLS - Direct sintering of material powders by a laser
2. FDM - Mini extrusion of powder filled thermoplastic polymers
3. DLP - Optical polymerisation of powder filled resins
4. PBP - Printing / jetting binder on a powder bed

As with the metal AM machines, most of the details listed are guidelines and dependent on the materials as well as the specific design of the component. Some of the key details are shown in Table 7.

Table 7: A summary of the capabilities of the ceramic technologies.

Technology	Feature size (mm)	Comparative tolerance	Max size (mm)
SLS	0.2	Average	50
FDM	1	Worst	200
DLP	0.05	Best	100
PBP	0.2	Worst	100